

WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT OF SELECTED LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Managing logistics has been critical focus area for manufacturers, distributors and third-party logistics players in their pursuit of developing a lean, agile and efficient customer oriented supply chain. Among the biggest challenges these players face today is maintaining the delicate balance of increased material and transportation costs against the expectations of improved service levels mandated by customers. To achieve this end, many industry players are collaborating with their key customers and vendors to improve their processes and systems and provide better service quality, reduce costs and improve visibility. To gain full advantage of such collaborative initiatives, building an efficient and effective supply chain intelligence infrastructure is a must. To achieve better customer service at reduced costs, organizations are increasingly adopting the two layers of process improvement and technological breakthroughs in track-and-trace, improved control systems and IT innovations such as cloud platforms. To fully realize the benefits from these initiatives and move toward an era of continuous improvement in their operations, organizations will also need to realign their logistics performance measurement strategies. Performance management is a methodology to optimize the execution of business strategy. This study constitutes the fundament of a broader research, in which researcher examine working capital management of logistics service providers. Keeping it in view the present topic of research “Working capital Management of Selected Logistic Companies in India” has been taken to determine the financial performance of Logistics Companies in India.

Keywords: Logistics, Company, Performance, Financial, Management, Appraisal

INTRODUCTION

Logistics is the management of the flow of goods between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet some requirements, of customers or corporations. The resources managed in logistics can include physical items, such as food, materials, animals, equipment and liquids, as well as abstract items, such as time, information, particles, and energy. The logistics of physical items usually involves the integration of information flow, material handling, production, packaging, inventory, transportation, warehousing, and often security. The

complexity of logistics can be modeled, analyzed, visualized, and optimized by dedicated simulation software. The minimization of the use of resources is a common motivation in logistics for import and export.

Logistics is chief gear of a booming economy in the world. It plays vital function in countrywide economy and is also significant contributor at both the national and local plane. It reinforces the economy, services, enabling the transportation of goods and people as proficiently as practicable. It is the flow of materials, information and money between clients and suppliers. It is a process by which one can move the goods or product from one place to other or from the tip of beginning to bottom point of utilization. It's an art and science of managing and controlling the flow of goods, products, services, energy, information and people from the source point to the destination point. It also includes numerous activities viz. material handling, warehousing and information, with the objective of ensuring delivery of the true product at the right time, place and cost in true condition.

The Indian logistics industry is probable to continue its growth impetus in coming years ahead. Unlike the previous years, this sector is forecasted to observe a consolidate signals in the coming months with the view of refreshing fortune of this sector due to the booming of end-user Industries. In 2014, the Indian logistics segment accounted revenues of about \$82.10 billion, witnessing a growth about 9.2 per cent over the previous year driven by strong growth of key manufacturing industry sectors. For the era 2010-2020, the Indian logistics market is to be expected consistent annual growth of all around 8-9 per cent and will attain to the revenue level of about \$190-200 billion by the end 2020. This target will only be achieved with the assistance of steady growth of the economy and contribution of major industries sectors like engineering, pharmaceuticals, automotive, food processing and others.

Therefore in this backdrop the present study is formulated to investigate Working capital Management of Selected Logistic Companies in India

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brent D. Williams(Department of Marketing and Logistics, Sam M. Walton College of Business, University of Arkansas, Fayetteville, Arkansas, USA), Travis Tokar(The Ohio State University, Fisher College of Business, Marketing and Logistics, Columbus, Ohio, USA), (2008), "A review of inventory management research in major logistics journals: Themes and future directions", published in The International Journal of Logistics Management, Two major themes are found to emerge from logistics research focused on inventory management. First, logistics researchers have focused considerable attention on integrating traditional logistics decisions, such as transportation and warehousing, with inventory management decisions, using traditional inventory control models. Second, logistics researchers have more recently focused on examining inventory management through collaborative models.

Gyöngyi Kovács (Swedish School of Economics and Business Administration (Hanken), Helsinki, Finland) and Karen M. Spens (Swedish School of Economics and Business Administration (Hanken), Helsinki, Finland) (2007) "Humanitarian logistics in disaster relief operations", published in International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Creates a framework distinguishing between actors, phases, and logistical processes of disaster relief. Drawing parallels of humanitarian logistics and business logistics, the paper discovers and describes the unique characteristics of humanitarian logistics while recognizing the need of humanitarian logistics to learn from business logistics.

Brian J. Gibson Ph.D., John T. Mentzer Ph.D. and Robert L. Cook Ph.D. (2005) "Supply Chain Management-Role of Logistics professionals" published in "Journal of Business Logistics" cited that, As disciplines evolve, it is a normal part of the maturation process to regularly examine the definition of the discipline — i.e., what the discipline is and is not. The opinions of those involved in the discipline are key to this maturation (i.e., definitional) process. Developing a consensus definition of supply chain management is a widely discussed but unresolved challenge. Thus, the current study provides insight into the perceptions of logistics professionals regarding this issue based upon an Internet-based survey.

METHODOLOGY

The study was descriptive and exploratory in nature. Secondary data were collected from the published annual reports and accounts of the Companies under study. The journals, magazines Government Publications for Business and Trade, Foreign Business Publications, Technical and Trade Journals, Books related to Management, Business Magazines, Reports and Publication of various associations connected with Business and Industry, Reports prepared by research scholars, universities & economists, Public records, Statistics and Internet and newspapers will also be used to collect the required information.

OBJECTIVES:

- i. To determine the working capital ratios of selected logistic industries in India
- ii. To suggest remedial measures for better financial position of Logistic Industries in India.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

Working capital management is the way a company manages the relationship between assets and liabilities in the short term. Simply put, working capital management is how a company manages its money for day to day operations as well as any immediate debt obligations. When managing working capital, the company has to manage accounts receivable, accounts payable, inventory,

and cash. The goal of working capital management is to have adequate cash flow for continued operations and have the most productive usage of resources.

There are a few calculations we have to discuss in regards to working capital management. To calculate working capital, a company would take current assets and subtract current liabilities.

Working capital efficiency is determined by calculating the working capital ratio. This ratio is a key indicator in the company's financial health. The working capital efficiency is calculated by taking current assets divided by current liabilities. If the result of the calculation is less than 1.0, then it is taken as a sign that the company's having financial issues. If the result of the calculation is greater than 1.0 but less than 2.0, then the company is in good financial health. If the calculation yields a result greater than 2.0, then company may not be making an effective use of its assets.

(a) Current Ratio

The current ratio is a liquidity and efficiency ratio that measures a firm's ability to pay off its short-term liabilities with its current assets. The current ratio is an important measure of liquidity because short-term liabilities are due within the next year.

This means that a company has a limited amount of time in order to raise the funds to pay for these liabilities. Current assets like cash, cash equivalents, and marketable securities can easily be converted into cash in the short term. This means that companies with larger amounts of current assets will more easily be able to pay off current liabilities when they become due without having to sell off long-term, revenue generating assets.

The formula for Current Ratio is – Current Assets/ Current Liabilities

TABLE –1 CURRENT RATIO OF SELECTED FIVE LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN INDIA

YEAR → COMPANY ↓	11-12	12-13	13-14	14-15	15-16	AVE.	S.D.	C.V.	Min	Max
TNT EXPRESS	1.14	1.23	1.34	1.24	1.15	1.22	0.080	6.63	1.14	1.34
BLUE DART	2.37	2.90	0.50	0.17	1.82	1.55	1.180	76.06	0.17	2.90
GATI	0.79	3.65	0.74	0.64	0.85	1.33	1.296	97.22	0.64	3.65
SAFE XPRESS	1.13	0.75	1.72	1.93	1.77	1.46	0.499	34.20	0.75	1.93
AGARWAL PACKERS ANDS MOVERS	2.71	2.11	1.97	1.92	2.01	2.14	0.324	15.11	1.92	2.71

CHART – 1 CURRENT RATIO OF SELECTED FIVE LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN INDIA

TREND ANALYSIS-

The above table 1 shows the current ratio of five logistic companies. The current ratio helps investors and creditors understand the liquidity of a company and how easily that company will be able to pay off its current liabilities. This ratio expresses a firm's current debt in terms of current assets. So a current ratio of 4 would mean that the company has 4 times more current assets than current liabilities. The five companies which are listed in the table are TNT Express, Blue Dart, Gati, Safexpress and Agarwal packers and movers.

The first company is TNT Express which had 1.34 as its maximum current ratio in the year 2013-14 and 1.14 as its minimum ratio in the year 2011-12. The mean value of this company was 1.22 and standard deviation was 0.080. The company had a decent current ratio.

In table 4.1 the second company was Blue Dart with a mean value and standard deviation of 1.55 and 1.180 respectively. The company’s maximum and minimum ratio was 2.90 in 2012-13 and 0.17 in 2014-15.

The third company in the table was Gati with highest ratio of 3.65 in the year 2012-13 and lowest ratio of 0.64 in the year 2014-15. The company's ratio didn't had much fluctuation. The mean value of Gati was 1.33 and standard deviation was 1.296.

In table 4.5, the fourth company was Safexpress with the highest ratio of 1.93 in the year 2014-15 and the lowest ratio of 0.75 in the year 2012-13. The company was performing better as the ratios were quite decent.

The last company enlisted in the table was Agarwal packers and movers with the mean value of 2.14 and the coefficient of variance was 15.11. In the year 2011-12 the company had its maximum current ratio of 2.71 and in the year 2014-15 the company had its minimum ratio of 1.92.

(b) QUICK RATIO

The quick ratio or acid test ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures the ability of a company to pay its current liabilities when they come due with only quick assets. Quick assets are current assets that can be converted to cash within 90 days or in the short-term. Cash, cash equivalents, short-term investments or marketable securities, and current accounts receivable are considered quick assets.

Short-term investments or marketable securities include trading securities and available for sale securities that can easily be converted into cash within the next 90 days. Marketable securities are traded on an open market with a known price and readily available buyers. Any stock on the New York Stock Exchange would be considered a marketable security because they can easily be sold to any investor when the market is open.

The quick ratio is often called the acid test ratio in reference to the historical use of acid to test metals for gold by the early miners. If the metal passed the acid test, it was pure gold. If metal failed the acid test by corroding from the acid, it was a base metal and of no value.

The acid test of finance shows how well a company can quickly convert its assets into cash in order to pay off its current liabilities. It also shows the level of quick assets to current liabilities.

The quick ratio is calculated by adding cash, cash equivalents, short-term investments, and current receivables together then dividing them by current liabilities.

$$\text{Quick ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash} + \text{cash equivalents} + \text{Short term investments} + \text{Current receivables}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Sometimes company financial statements don't give a breakdown of quick assets on the balance sheet. In this case, you can still calculate the quick ratio even if some of the quick asset totals are unknown. Simply subtract inventory and any current prepaid assets from the current asset total for the numerator.

$$\text{Quick ratio} = \frac{\text{Total current assets} - \text{Inventory} - \text{prepaid expenses}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$$

The acid test ratio measures the liquidity of a company by showing its ability to pay off its current liabilities with quick assets. If a firm has enough quick assets to cover its total current liabilities, the firm will be able to pay off its obligations without having to sell off any long-term or capital assets.

Since most businesses use their long-term assets to generate revenues, selling off these capital assets will not only hurt the company it will also show investors that current operations aren't making enough profits to pay off current liabilities.

TABLE –2 QUICK RATIO OF SELECTED FIVE LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN INDIA

YEAR → COMPANY ↓	11-12	12-13	13-14	14-15	15-16	AVE.	S.D.	C.V.	Min	Max
TNT EXPRESS	1.13	1.35	1.35	1.24	1.16	1.24	0.10	0.08	1.13	1.35
BLUE DART	2.01	2.27	2.06	1.87	2.10	2.06	0.14	0.07	1.87	2.27
GATI	2.64	1.61	1.48	1.44	1.44	1.72	0.51	0.30	1.44	2.64
SAFE XPRESS	1.59	0.82	2.51	1.25	1.24	1.48	0.63	0.42	0.82	2.51
AGARWAL PACKERS ANDS MOVERS	1.29	1.18	1.16	1.68	1.59	1.38	0.24	0.17	1.16	1.68

CHART – 2 QUICK RATIO OF SELECTED FIVE LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN INDIA

TREND ANALYSIS

From the above table the quick ratio of selected five logistic companies in India has been analyzed. Higher quick ratios are more favorable for companies because it shows there are more quick assets than current liabilities. A company with a quick ratio of 1 indicates that quick assets equal current assets. This also shows that the company could pay off its current liabilities without selling any long-term assets. A quick ratio of 2 shows that the company has twice as many quick assets than current liabilities. Obviously, as the ratio increases so does the liquidity of the company. More assets will be easily converted into cash if need be. This is a good sign for investors but an even better sign to creditors because creditors want to know they will be paid back on time.

The first company under logistics was TNT express with a minimum quick ratio of 1.13 in the year 2011-12 whereas the maximum quick ratio was 1.35 in the year 2012-13 respectively. The mean value and standard deviation was calculated as 1.24 and 0.10 for TNT express. The second company was Blue dart with coefficient of variance of 0.07 and its mean value was marked as 2.06. The minimum and maximum quick ratio was 1.87 and 2.27 in the year 2014-15 and 2012-13. The third company under logistics was Gati with a mean value and standard deviation of 1.72 and 0.51. Its minimum ratio was calculated as 1.44 in the year 2014 to 2016 whereas the maximum ratio was 2.64 in the year 2011-12. In the fourth company named as Safe Xpress, the standard deviation and coefficient of variance was calculated as 0.63 and 0.42. The minimum and maximum quick ratio of Safe Xpress was 0.82 and 2.51 in the year 2012-13 and 2013-14 respectively. The last company under logistics was Agarwal packers and movers with a mean value of 1.38 whereas the standard deviation was 0.24. Its minimum quick ratio was 1.16 in the year 2013-14 whereas the maximum ratio was marked as 1.68 in the year 2014-15.

So, after analyzing the above table ratios, it can be concluded that Blue dart had the best quick ratio throughout five years as it had a quick ratio of more than 2 constantly all the year followed by Gati and Agarwal packers and movers.

Statistical Analysis

Thus the current Null Hypothesis H_0 : There is no significant difference in the working capital of the companies under study can be tested with statistical analysis on the above Current Ratio Table 1 .

Above Hypotheses was analyzed by applying Leven's test for equality of variance followed by t test on above variable:-

Table 3 (ANALYSIS TABLE)

Independent Samples Test										
VARIABLE AND LOGISTIC COMPANY_TYPE		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Current Ratio (Working Capital)	All Five Selected Logistic Companies	7.001	.009	-2.838	148	.005	-0.23	0.08	-0.39	-0.07

Above hypotheses testing interperates that as the t tailed value for current ratio (Working Capital Management) of Selected Logistics Company is 0.005 seems to be extremely significant in above variable, it can be postulated that **Null Hypotheses H_0 : There is no significant difference in the working capital of the companies under study is *rejected*** and **Alternate Hypotheses H_1 : There exists a significant difference in the working capital of the companies under study is *accepted and Proved*.**

CONCLUSION

Logistics is the management of the flow of goods between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet some requirements, of customers or corporations. The resources managed in logistics can include physical items, such as food, materials, animals, equipment and liquids, as well as abstract items, such as time, information, particles, and energy. The logistics of physical items usually involves the integration of information flow, material handling, production, packaging, inventory, transportation, warehousing, and often security.

India's logistics sector attracted huge investments, leaving behind some of the major sectors including aviation, metals, and consumer durables. The growth in the retail and manufacturing industry, commodity markets and development of SEZs has also been the key factors in the growth of Indian logistics industry. Recent studies indicate that the Indian logistics industry is expected to grow annually at the rate of 15 to 20 per cent. A number of infrastructural projects involving warehouse and logistics parks are being undertaken and they are expected to be operational in the coming next 2-3 years.

In spite of the increased focus on logistics by most companies, the gap is widening between logistics cost leaders and laggards. Logistics leaders are unlocking the value of the enterprise across the value chain. Some of the key trends influencing logistics decisions are as

follows: Organizational focus on managing logistics Costs The total cost of logistics for a typical company is 7% to 12% of sales and is growing due to increasing supply chain complexities. Thus, there is an increased focus from corporate management on controlling and managing this cost. Logistics costs typically follow economic cycles. During times of growth, the available capacity becomes constrained, and rates rise. When recession hits, rates fall due to competition among service providers to utilize the surplus capacity. Managing capacity and utilization is often a tightrope walk for most service providers and proves to be a differentiating factor for most companies.

As part of the functions of operations management, logistics plays an important role in transporting the flow of goods in and out of the company. The company need to facilitate the smooth flow of incoming raw materials (inbound) to the company with the aim to facilitate the operations. The proper inbound management will impact several aspect in the company, such as, on production schedules, distribution effectiveness, customer satisfaction and firm performance (Tracey, 2005). In fact, despite the role of logisticsis facilitating the incoming flows, logistics is also facilitating the outcome delivery. This role of logistics is expected to provide a better improvement of the quality of raw materials and the accuracy of the amount of raw material by the company. In other words, the logistics role should optimize the flow of goods in order to maintain quality, on time delivery and satisfaction. Therefore, the capability of logistics to manage both these flows will enhance the value added and have an impact on maintain the business performance.

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